

Integrated Digital Platform to Improve Transparency and Efficiency in Contract Farming

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Abstract—Agriculture in Karnataka is increasingly getting affected as the availability of farm labour is decreasing and the number of unused cultivable land is increasing. This happens because most youth consider farming less reliable source of income. As a result, the younger generations are moving to cities in search of stable income and better job opportunities. As a result, the cultivable lands are left unused.

This research presents a digital agricultural land leasing platform using blockchain technology to ensure transparency and accountability. This framework incorporates Aadhaar-based e-KYC for identity verification of the participants, smart contracts to automate the generation of land leasing agreements, GIS-based land mapping and escrow-based payment that secure the transactions. By integrating these features, the system aims to improve trust, reduce disputes and improve the utilization of land. This system helps to improve the overall performance as it overcomes the difficulties faced during manual coordination. The study aligns with national initiatives such as Digital India and Atmanirbhar Bharat. The study also highlights the potential of digital technologies in strengthening the agricultural systems in India.

Keywords— Contract Farming, Digital Land Leasing, GIS based mapping, Aadhar e-KYC, Smart Contracts, Escrow Payments.

I. INTRODUCTION

Contract farming is an important development in agriculture. It provides a modern way in agriculture where an agreement is made between farmers and the buyers. Here, since agreement is created, the farmers have a reliable market and they get a stable income based on the pre-agreed price. In traditional farming, farmers have to face price fluctuations and find buyers for their product. As a result, farmers face issues such as unstable income. This makes farming less reliable. Contract farming overcomes all these challenges by providing price, assurance, a reliable market and better-quality seeds as input. This helps small and medium-scale farmers to generate better income and improve the crop production. Contract farming started in developed countries like the United States in the 19th century. During that time, agribusinesses and food processing industries needed a regular supply of raw materials. To ensure steady supply of raw materials, the companies made agreements with farmers which mentioned the crop details, quality standards and when the produce should be delivered. Since the system worked well, it was adopted in other parts of the world including Europe, Latin America, Africa and Asia. Over time, contract

farming changed from simple buying agreements to providing farmers with seeds, training and financial support.

Contract farming has helped to connect the farmers around the globe. In Latin America, contract farming is used for crops like coffee, sugarcane and soybeans. In Southeast Asia, it is used for high value crops like fruits and vegetables. In Africa, it is used for crops such as cotton, tea and cashew. These examples showed the effectiveness of contract farming if implemented properly with fair and transparent contract. If the contracts are not managed properly, it will lead to disputes and unfair sharing of profits. In India, contract farming was introduced to modernize farming that helped to connect farmers to the formal supply chain. It is used in states like Punjab, Haryana, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka for crops like gherkins, tomatoes and mangoes. The Government of India also introduced Model Contract Farming Act to make contracts fair, transparent and trustworthy. This helped farmers a lot in gaining stable income and fair share of profits. Still, many difficulties remained including limited awareness among the farmers and weak enforcement of agreements.

Karnataka has immense potential for the development of contract farming because of its fertile land, diverse climatic conditions and strong agribusiness sector. Karnataka has already achieved success in the crops such as mangoes, gherkins and grapes with the partnership with companies like ITC and PepsiCo. However, many farmers have small landholdings and limited resources which made contract farming difficult. So, there is a need overcome all these problems which help in long-term development of contract farming all over the world.

Digital technologies can help to overcome these challenges. For example, farmers can temporarily combine plots for farming a crop. Digital technologies can help connect farmers, mapping of the agricultural plots, identity verification, secure payment methods and better coordination among farmers. Combining digital land leasing with contract farming can create a system that is efficient, transparent and supportive for farmers, landowners and agribusiness companies.

Contract farming has economic, social and environmental benefits. Contract farming helps farmers to generate stable income which economically benefit the farmers. Socially, contract framing promotes farmers to develop their skills and share knowledge. Environmentally, it helps in sustainable development of agriculture. However, for the development of contract farming we need appropriate policies, reliable digital tools and strong institutional support

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Contract farming is an efficient way to connect farmers to agribusinesses, exporters and food processing companies. Contract farming helps farmers gain stable income, technical guidance while agribusinesses also benefitted from the steady supply of good-quality products. In this section earlier papers related to contract farming, digital technologies in contract farming, GIS based land mapping are reviewed which helps to understand how these studies have improved the transparency and efficiency in agricultural industry.

Meemken and Bellemere [1] studied contract farming in six developing countries and found that the system helped farmers generate a stable income and also creates better job opportunities. However, the study also found that the benefits are not equally distributed. Some farmers gain more than others which highlights the need for more inclusive and transparent agricultural system. Similarly, Ogotu, Ochieng, and Qaim [2] studied contract farming through supermarket in Kenya. They found that the farmers who were involved in contract farming earned 40% more income and faced less poverty when compared to non-contract farmers. However, wealthier farmers gained higher profits while the small-scale farmers benefited from better living conditions rather than gaining high cash income.

In India, Paltasingh et al. [3] studied contract farming among wheat farmers in Haryana and found that the farmers involved in contract farming showed better performance as they had the access to better quality 2 inputs and modern farming practices. The study also highlighted the challenges such as high production cost and delays in receiving payments.

Peng et al. [4] proposed a blockchain based model for the rice supply chain. The model uses smart contracts to automate the creation of agreements and cross-chain mechanism to enhance the transparency. This system also helped to improve the data security. Simulation results showed quicker transactions and improved traceability, indicating blockchain can improve the reliability and efficiency of agricultural supply chains.

Montenegro Hernandez [5] reviewed earlier studies and found that blockchain-based supply chain can reduce fraudulent activities, improve food safety and build trust among all the participants. The study also pointed out that real-world implementations of blockchain are limited and there is a need of stronger frameworks for better implementation. Other studies [6], [12] also found that integrating blockchain and IoT can automate the overall contract process and increase the trust among farmers and buyers. Benjamin [7] studied land ownership and agricultural investments in Malawi and found that agricultural productivity is influenced by the social factors such as women's land rights. Kamau et al. [8] and Mathenge [9] used GIS and remote sensing techniques to assess the land suitability for the crops like potatoes. Their study found that GIS-based evaluation of agricultural land helps to find the suitable farming areas and improve the land use. Thapliyal et al. [10] used the GIS techniques in Yamuna Basin of Uttarkashi and found that combining the data on water, soil and topography helped in better irrigation planning. In Ethiopia, Hirpesa et al. [11] found that farmers participation in contract farming mainly depends on factors like access to credit and agricultural training.

Stanescu et al. [12] studied the role of various technologies like Artificial intelligence, blockchain and IOT in improving the transparency and sustainability of the food supply chain. The CTSAF framework demonstrated that integrating these technologies help in promoting circular economic models. These technologies also support transparent systems. Taherdoost [13] studied about how smart contracts are used in blockchain systems. The study found that even though smart contracts are useful it still has various challenges such as scalability, interoperability and security issues. Further research and improvements required to overcome all these challenges. Shakthi [14] explained the role of national identity systems like Aadhaar in identity verification and data security. This is useful for creating blockchain-based identity systems in agriculture. Li et al. [15] developed a GIS-based system which helps to assess the suitability of the land. This helps farmers to make better agricultural decisions. Combining this with blockchain based systems improves the reliability and transparency of the system. Matekele et al. [16] studied how farmers in Tanzania choose agricultural financial systems and found that their decisions primarily depend on various factors such as the usefulness of the system, intensity of the risk involved and their level of awareness. Maertens and Swinnen [17] and Maertens and Verhofstadt [18] found that export-oriented farmers help small farmers to earn stable income, but there should be inclusion policies which helps everyone to gain the benefits. Recent studies [19]–[22] studied about how blockchain can be combined with IOT and smart contracts in agriculture. The systems like Agri-BC were designed which helped to make farming more transparent, automate processes and reduce the dependency on middlemen. GIS and remote sensing-based land assessments [21], [22], [24] also proved useful in finding suitable land and promote sustainable development of farming.

II. RESEARCH GAP AND OBJECTIVE

Previous studies have examined the advantages and challenges of contract framing, blockchain based system and GIS based land mapping. But there are very few studies that links these two areas which is contract farming and blockchain based identity systems and GIS-based evaluation for land mapping. Most existing research focuses separately on blockchain based system or contracts to enhance the productivity and transparency. There is still a lack of an integrated system that connects farmers, landowners and agribusinesses through smart contracts, identity verification and real-time land data.

Additionally, many studies have reported problems such as unequal distribution of benefits, lack of trust, poor interoperability between digital tools, and limited awareness or policy support for adopting new technologies in agriculture. The main research focus is on developing and testing a digital platform for contract farming and land leasing that uses blockchain technology. The platform is aimed at providing transparency, fairness and efficiency. It can help to connect social and economic needs with technology, especially in states like Karnataka where they face problems with finding appropriate land and labour. The next section explains how blockchain and GIS-based land mapping can be combined to create a platform for the sustainable development of contract farming.

A. Problem Identification

Even though Karnataka has immense potential for agricultural development, there are various problems such as

fragmented landholdings, lack of farm labors, informal land leasing and frequent disputes over payments. These structural issues adversely affect the development of agriculture in Karnataka.

1. Shortage of Farm Labor

One of the major issues faced by agricultural sector in Karnataka is shortage of labour. Agriculture is often considered as unreliable as it doesn't provide stable income. As a result, younger generations are migrating to cities for stable income and better living conditions. This has left many agricultural cultivable lands unused. Farming is often considered risky, hard work and less profitable when compared to city jobs. As a result, farmers don't find enough workers to do various agricultural tasks like planting, watering and harvesting crops. As a result, cultivable land is left unused and overall farm production has reduced.

2. Idle and Fragmented land owned by Non-Residents

Another major issue in Karnataka is farmland is small, scattered and left unused. Many landowners live in cities or work in non-farming jobs which has left their land unused. AS a result, there are large number of cultivable unused land. Also, as the lands are scattered it is difficult to do large scale farming or use machines effectively.

3. Informal Land-Leasing Arrangements

Land leasing is a very common practice in rural Karnataka where landowners rent their land to farmers for cultivation. These agreements are usually verbal which give little to no security. These often leads to disputes between landowners and farmers. Since there is no legal document, landowners.

4. Frequent Payment Delays and Disputes in Manual Contracts

Traditional leasing often involves agreements made through verbal communication instead of nay legal documents. This often leads to disputes between landowners and tenants. This involves issues like delay 4 in payments, not paying the amount on which both parties agreed. All these issues demotivate the framers, agribusinesses and food processing companies from getting into contract farming even though they have mutual interest.

C. Objectives of the study

The primary objective of this study is to design a conceptual framework that provides transparent, secure and efficient way for contract farming and land leasing. This study aims to build a structural model instead of complete working model which can later be implemented to solve real agricultural problems. The study also discusses how digital technologies can connect landowners, agribusinesses and farmers through a trusted and transparent platform. This digital platform aims to provide transparency, accountability and legal protection to everyone involved.

Objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To Verify the identity of landowners and farmers through Aadhaar-based identification Here the system aims to verify the identity of the users using Aadhaar-KYC which helps build trust between the participants. This also helps to reduce fraudulent activities.
2. GIS-based land mapping for the verification of the farmland Here the system focuses on using GIS technology to verify the farmland boundary and ownership details. This helps the system find the land's size, location and condition, which

helps to reduce confusion before a land leasing agreement is made.

3. To introduce transparent smart digital contracts that are legally valid: This objective aims to use blockchain-based smart contracts as digital agreements for land leasing. These agreements improve transparency as they make sure that agreed terms are automatically followed. This helps to reduce human errors thereby reducing disputes.

4. to implement a secure payment system using escrow-based payment system: The model also integrates escrow- based payment method which ensures that money is kept safely until the agreed conditions are met. This ensures timely payment and protect farmers and landowners from payment related fraud.

5. To encourage effective land utilization and sustainable development of contract farming: This system aims to build a secure digital platform that improves the participation of farmers and landowners. This digital system motivates landowners in leasing their land and agribusinesses in using the land productively. This leads to overall growth of agricultural sector and improve rural livelihoods.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses design and conceptual approach to design a framework for digital land leasing platform. The goal is to improve the transparency, security and efficiency in agricultural land leasing. Instead of building the complete system, the study focuses on designing the model which verifies the identity, automates the creation of digital agreements and secures the payment. The study aims to overcome the challenges faced in traditional farming systems. The proposed methodology follows four stages:

- Data collection and review
- System Design
- Technology Planning
- Validation through simulation

Each stage is planned to examine how the digital platform can make the land leasing process transparent, trustworthy and easy to access for both farmers and landowners.

A. Data Collection and Review

This stage of research focused on gathering official government documents, research papers and policy documents to study how contract farming and land leasing is working currently in Karnataka. This aimed at finding the problems and gaps in existing systems and to find how digital tools like blockchain, Aadhaar e-KYC and GIS can address these issues effectively.

a. Sources of Data

Secondary sources were used for data collection. These include:

1. Government Reports:

Information was gathered from government and institutional reports such as the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, NABARD and ICAR. These reports helped to understand farming practices in Karnataka such as crops grown and seasonal farming practices. They also explained the major problems faced by farmers such as labour shortage, limited access to modern technologies, fragmented landholdings and payment disputes. These reports helped in understanding the government schemes such as soil health

cards, crop insurance that supports farmers. It was found that several districts such as Tumakuru, Hasan and Mandya faced labour shortages. According to the State Level Bankers Committee around 59% of the total land is under cultivation. This shows that around 40% of cultivable land is left unused. CEIC data shows that around 2,266 thousand hectares of land are officially classified as “Not available for cultivation” and another 1,479 thousand hectares are classified as “Other uncultivable land”. This statistic itself shows the presence of large areas of agricultural land left unused. These statistics helped in understanding the gaps in existing systems and the need for digital solutions to improve the overall land usage.

Table 1: Areas not available for cultivation

Reporting Area for Land Utilization: Not available for cultivation in Karnataka			
Year	Not available for cultivation	Area under non-agricultural uses	Barren and uncultivable land
2003-04	2123.65	1335.7	787.95
2008-09	2162.68	1375.05	787.63
2013-14	2230.24	1443.63	786.61
2018-19	2274	1505	769
2023-24	2312	1573	740

Source: Ministry of agriculture and Farmers Welfare.

1. Legal and Policy Documents:

In this, important laws and policies such as Model Agricultural Land Leasing Act (2016), the Karnataka land Reforms Act, and tenancy rules were examined to understand how agricultural lands were legally managed. This helped to understand the rules related to lease agreements, rent and the right of landowners and tenants. It also helped to understand the challenges faced by the current system such as poor implementation and less awareness of laws which showed the possibility of digital contracts that follows legal rules. A recent report revealed that many agricultural lands in Karnataka are still registered under the names of deceased owners. This leads to various problems while leasing land including the issues like absentee ownership and legal issues. These findings helped in understanding the existing legal problems which helped in building a framework that overcome these challenges.

2. Academic Research Various research papers and reports from Scopus-indexed journals and other journals were reviewed. This analysis helped to understand challenges and benefits of contract farming. This also helped in understanding how technologies like digital identity verification, smart contracts and GIS based land mapping and blockchain are being used in agriculture. In addition to this case studies of different countries were also analyzed to understand how technology can improve trust, reliability and transparency in farming practices. Research published in Junikhyat Journal (2020) and IJRAR (2019) showed that average farm size has reduced from 3.2 hectares in 1970 to 1.63 hectares in 2016. This increase in land fragmentation has increased the difficulty of doing contract farming. These findings show the importance of integrating digital technologies into contract farming in Karnataka.

Table 2:

Fallow lands in Karnataka

Reporting area for land utilization: Fallow lands in Karnataka			
Year	Fallow lands: Total (thousand hectares)	Fallow lands other than current fallow (Thousand hectares)	Current fallows(Thousand hectares)
2003-04	2341.5	487.35	1853.7
2008-09	2015.73	515.97	1499.76
2013-14	2225.18	525.24	1699.94
2018-19	1511	571	940
2023-24	1600	475	1126

Source: Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare

4. Agricultural, social and economic statistics:

Information on fragmented landholdings, absentee ownership, land use, idle land, labour availability, impact of urban migration on agricultural productivity were gathered from Agricultural Census of India (2021-22) and Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Karnataka. In addition to this, CEIC data showed that around 20% of cultivable land in Karnataka either lies as fallow or under “other uncultivated land”. Rural migration has also affected agricultural productivity leaving many cultivable lands unused. This understanding of current challenges showed the need for a digital platform that connect farmers, labours and landowners.

Table 3:

Other uncultivated land excluding fallow land in Karnataka

Reporting area for land utilisation: Other uncultivated land excluding fallow land in Karnataka			
Year	Other uncultivable land excluding fallow land: Total(Thousand Hectares)	Permanent pastures and other grazing lands(Thousand hectares)	Land under miscellaneous tree crops and groves not included in net area sown
2003-04	1667.59	947.16	301.1
2008-09	1626.01	923.38	289.7
2013-14	1597.93	906.26	281.2
2018-19	1527	872	251
2023-24	1363	872	177

b. Review of Existing Systems

A detailed study on the existing systems helped to find the challenges in the current contract framing and leasing systems. In India, most of leasing agreements are informal through verbal communication. This often leads to disputes and financial risks. Challenges such as delayed payments, unclear land boundaries and fragmented land holdings discourage landowners and agribusinesses from entering into these contracts. Studies also show that around 70% of leasing in southern states are informal. Although there are various digital initiatives like mobile app for crop trading and farmer registration, these do not provide complete solution such as identity verification, land verification, secure payments and smart contracts. This review clearly shows the challenges faced by the current system which emphasizes the need for an integrated digital solution.

c. Legal and Policy Review

The legal and policy review was done to understand the existing laws related to land leasing and contract farming and to find the problems with the existing systems. The Karnataka Land Reforms Act and tenancy rules showed that there is a lack of legal protection and transparency for informal leasing agreements and lands owned by absentee landowners. The Model Agricultural Land Leasing Act (2016) helped landowners to easily lease their land, but it was not widely used in Karnataka as it was not properly implemented. Currently, there is no such systems which combines legal protection with digital technologies. The reason behind this is lack of digital awareness among the rural population and lack of simple online systems for registering lease agreements. Therefore, there is a need of a digital platform that provide secure, transparent and legally valid land leasing process.

d. Technology Review

Technological reviews were conducted to identify the potential tools that can be integrated into the proposed digital model. Blockchain Technology provides a tamper proof way to store records, automate the creation of agreements through smart contracts and helps in transparent payment tracking. Aadhaar e KYC helps in verifying the identity of farmers and landowners thereby reducing unauthorized activities. GIS and remote sensing helped to understand the boundaries, size of land and suitability of the land. Case studies from Andhra Pradesh's e-Crop booking system and Telangana's Dharani portal demonstrate that digital verification tools can reduce land disputes by up to 40%.

e. Analytical Insights

Several important issues were found by analyzing government reports, legal frameworks and technology-based framework together. Large amount of agricultural land is left unused due to shortage of labor, absentee landowners and fragmented land holdings. Also, most of the land leasing agreements are informal which often lead to disputes and payment issues. Existing government digital platforms and mobile applications are not fully connected with important features like identity verification, smart contracts and land boundary verification. However, technologies like blockchain, Aadhaar-based identity verification and GIS have strong potential to work together and build secure, transparent and legally compliant digital platform that can effectively solve all these problems.

f. Outcome of Review

The data collected and reviewed provided a strong foundation in designing proposed conceptual model. The study shows that combining Aadhar-based identity verification, blockchain based smart contracts and GIS mapping helps to build transparent, secure, efficient platform for contract farming. A single platform can reduce disputes, improve participation and promote sustainable agricultural development in Karnataka. These findings shows that the proposed model is practical, relevant and align with current technologies and legal frameworks.

B. System Design

This stage of research focuses on designing the conceptual system architecture for the proposed digital contract farming model. The architecture involves five core module which handles different stages of digital land leasing process. The goal of this framework is to create secure, transparent and user-friendly platform that can be easily used by both farmers and landowners. The first module is User registration and Verification. This step handles the process of registration and verification of the users using Aadhaar-based digital authentication. This step ensures that the users are uniquely identified and verified which prevents fraudulent activities and unauthorized access. The verification follows government approved e-KYC standards, making the system secure, transparent and legally compliant. The second module is GIS-based land mapping. This helps to identify land location, boundaries and size. This reduces ownership disputes and further improves transparency and security in the land leasing process. The third module is smart Lease Contract Management. This helps farmers and landowners create digital lease agreements according to the agreed conditions and are digitally signed using blockchain technology. Blockchain provide immutable, tamper proof way to store the records. These contracts can be easily accessed whenever required for verification or for dispute resolution. The fourth module is Escrow-based payment system. Here the payment from the farmers is held in an escrow account until all the conditions in the contract are met. When both the parties confirm that the conditions are met, the payment is released automatically to the landowners. This avoids payment delays and add financial security to the system. The fifth module is multi-lingual user interface. This focuses on making the platform user-friendly. Since, India has many languages, multiple language support helps users with limited education and technical skills. This will lead to wider adoption of the system. Together these features create a single unified digital system that brings together identity verification, accurate land mapping, secure payment support and multi-language support. The design ensures that the system is technologically robust, socially inclusive and practically operational for use in real agricultural applications.

C. Technology stack

Although this research doesn't include actual implementation, technology stack has been proposed that can be used for the actual future implementation. The technologies has been selected so that it provides scalability, security and accessibility of the platform on both mobile phones and web browsers. The frontend layer, which represents user interface can be built using React.js or flutter. These frameworks help in creating an interactive and responsive applications that can run smoothly on web

browsers and mobile devices. They make building application easy to use, quick to develop and easy to maintain. The backend layer, which handles data storage, business operations and system operations can be built using Node.js or Django. Both frameworks help in building robust backend. Node.js is suitable to build scalable systems and helps in real time communication while Django offers good security features and efficient data handling. For database system, PostgreSQL integrated with PostGIS can be used which helps in efficient handling of land related data such as land boundaries, coordinates, and mapping information. This helps in accurate storage, retrieval and analysis of land-related data which is need for land mapping and verification. Cloud Infrastructures like Amazon Web Services can be used for data storage and access. Cloud deployment helps multiple users from different regions to access the system. The platform also integrates various Application Programming Interfaces for identity verification and secure payment. For example, UIDAI API can be used to verify user identity, UPI API can be used for secure payment and also land record API can be used to connect with government databases for ownership details verification. Overall, this technology stacks helps to build a secure, transparent and reliable digital land leasing platform.

D. Validation and simulation

In the last stage of this study, validation of the system was done. This approach helped in understanding how the system performs in real world conditions without building the working software. For this purpose, hypothetical use cases were created to represent main stakeholders such as farmers, landowners and intermediaries. These use cases simulated activities such identity verification, land mapping, digital contract creation and payment handling. The aim of the simulation was to ensure the effectiveness of the system in providing security, transparency and efficiency in contract farming. Simulation was done to evaluate the effectiveness of each module of the system:

1. User Registration and Identity verification: Aadhaar based identity verification was simulated to find whether the system could securely verify user identities and help to prevent unauthorized access or prevent fraudulent activities. Land Mapping using GIS: Hypothetical geospatial data was collected to analyze whether the GIS-based land mapping securely verify the land boundaries and reduce disputes. Smart Lease Contract Management: Blockchain transactions were simulated to understand how digital lease agreements are created, signed and stored in tamper proof way. Escrow-based payment system: Virtual transactions were analyzed to ensure secure fund transfer between the farmers and landowners upon the fulfilment of contract conditions. Multilingual Interface: Theoretical simulation was done to confirm that multi-lingual interface could enhance the accessibility for the users with different education background and language proficiency. These simulations indicate the necessity of a unified digital land leasing platform in providing security, transparency and efficiency. Although actual implementation is not done, findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the system.

2. Application Layer

This layer carries out main operations such as creating digital contracts, searching and filtering land details and alerts related to payment confirmations and contract changes. This layer controls overall system functions and makes sure all the features work properly.

3. Integration Layer

This layer is used to integrate the platform to external systems like Aadhaar APIs for identity verification, UPI API for secure payment transactions, mapping services to verify land boundaries, ownership details, size and location details. This layer ensures platform communicates with external systems efficiently.

4. Database Layer

This layer securely stores all critical information such as user details, contract details, payment details and transaction histories. Proper encryption techniques are used to protect the data and proper organization ensures that information can be accessed and retrieved whenever required.

5. Security Layer

The security layer protects the platform from unauthorized access and data breaches. It protects the data using encryption techniques, control the access using Role Based Access, and add extra login security by using Multi-Factor Authentication. All the transactions are recorded with timestamp and digital signature, which makes all the actions traceable by the government whenever required.

A. Architecture Diagram

The five-layer system architecture is shown below in the diagram 5.1 which shows the interaction between each layer.

Figure 5.1: System Architecture of Digital Contract Farming Platform

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed platform is expected to improve the process of agricultural land leasing. The system is designed to provide secure, transparent and efficient platform for agricultural land leasing. One of the major benefits is the better utilization of agricultural land. The system connects land with farmer and agribusinesses which helps both the parties. Landowners get economic benefits and overall agricultural productivity can be increased. The system verifies the identity using Aadhaar-based Identity Verification protecting the system from unauthorized access and any type of fraudulent activity. Also, smart digital contracts provide clear, legally valid lease terms

which prevent disputes. Financial Security is also added by providing escrow-based payment which held the payment in escrow and only releases when the contract terms are fulfilled. The proposed land leasing platform can improve overall agricultural performance by 15-20% through better utilisation of agricultural lands. The system also give access to insurance through digitally verified land records and smart contract-based lease agreements.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

The proposed framework has immense potential of expansion and development. Key areas of future improvements include:

1. Field Testing:

Pilot testing can be done on different districts of Karnataka which helps to understand operational challenges, technical issues and user difficulties. The feedback collected from farmers, landowners and local authorities can help us identify issues related with the system. This helps to improve the system which can meet the requirements of all the stakeholders effectively.

2. IoT Sensors:

IoT sensors can be used to track soil condition, crop growth and overall farming productivity. These sensors give real time data such as soil moisture, nutrient levels and crop health. This can be integrated into the digital platform which can help automate processes such as checking the crop growth, extending land leases and payment release. This makes the system faster and also reduces human error.

3. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.

Artificial Intelligence and machine learning can be used to analyze large amount of data collected by the platform. These data can be used to make decisions such as better choice of crop for a particular land, fair lease conditions and decide reasonable prices for farmers and landowners. As the system continues to collect data, it can learn from the past results and improve the decision overtime. This makes the platform smarter and fully data-driven.

4. Policy Integration:

Connecting the platform with government programs helps farmers to easily access benefits such as subsidies, crop insurance and farm registration schemes. This also improves coordination between farmers, landowners, and government authorities. Overall, these enhancements will not only benefit all stakeholders but also contribute to sustainable agricultural development and improved land utilization.

VIII. APPLICATIONS AND CHALLENGES

A. Applications

The proposed framework has various applications:

1. Optimized Land Utilization:

The platform improves the utilization of farmland by connecting landowners and farmers and agribusinesses. This improves agricultural productivity and reduces wastage of farmland.

2. Secures Financial Transactions:

The Integration of Escrow-based payment secures transaction. Escrow-based payment method ensures that the payments are released only when the terms mentioned in the agreements are fulfilled reducing financial risk.

3. Legal Transparency and Trust Building:

Smart lease contracts provide legally valid agreements with terms and conditions. This reduces the chances of disputes and

build trust among farmers, landowners and other stakeholders.

4. Efficient Identity Verification:

Aadhaar-based Verification allows identity verification of users thereby reducing unauthorized access and fraudulent activities.

5. Data-driven Agricultural Planning:

GIS-based mapping helps to accurately identify, record the location and details of the land. These digital records help in better decision making, monitoring and policy planning for government agencies.

6. Empowerment of Rural labors and farmers:

The system promotes sustainable agricultural development by providing income opportunities to skilled labours, while reducing the dependency on manual labours.

B. Challenges

Despite advantages, the system also has challenges:

1. Digital Literacy:

Many rural farmers and landowners may be unfamiliar with smartphones, apps. So proper training has to be given to the users which helps them to use the platform effectively.

2. Internet Connectivity:

Another problem is internet connectivity. Access to reliable internet is very much limited in rural areas. Since system depends various online services such as Aadhaar Verification, land mapping, escrow-based payments, poor internet connectivity can affect the system usage.

3. Data Security:

Data security is very much essential for the system because it handles sensitive data such as identity verification, land details and financial records. So proper security measures such as encryption, data protection policies and proper authentication protocols are required to prevent unauthorized access.

4. User Trust and Acceptance:

Some farmers may be reluctant to use the platform and they may prefer traditional paper-based agreements over this digital system. So proper awareness has to be given to improve trust and encourage wider adoption.

5. Initial Costs and Technical Maintenance:

Setting up servers, maintaining security, integrating APIs and providing technical support are difficult. Small-scale projects may face difficulties to manage all these requirements.

IX. CONCLUSION

This research proposed a digital platform that helps farmers, landowners and other stakeholders to communicate better and trust each other. The proposed framework follows a five-layer architecture where each layer has specific role such as user interaction, application processing, data management, integration with other services and security. This structure makes the platform secure, transparent and easy to use. The results show that using digital tools in contract farming can reduce delay and helps in better organization of the data. Since the system provides real-time data, automates process and helps in secure data exchange, farmers and landowners can manage their farming activities more efficiently. The study also highlights the need of good internet connectivity and user-friendly interface for better adoption of the system, especially for rural communities.

IX. REFERENCES

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